

Scheme 1

reaction modes. Nucleophilic substitution of Cl⁻ by I⁻ in compound 1 (R=H) will lead to 2, which in turn can form 7 (R=H) through the carbanion 4 or can form 6 or 8 (R=H) through the carbenoids 3 and 5, respectively. Compounds 6 and 8 were not produced, since the tests for unsaturation were negative. The appearance of a signal at δ 4.8 in the ¹H nmr spectrum of the product supported the structure 7.

The reaction of I⁻ with α,α,α -trichlorotoluene is more facile than that with α,α -dichlorotoluene and yields a greater amount of the coupled product (Table 1). Moreover, the reaction time is less in dipolar aprotic solvents (DMF, CH₃CN) than in 2-propanol.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd.	M p °C	Yield %/(Reaction time).		
		D M F.	Aceto- nitrile	2-Pro- panol
C ₆ H ₅ CCl ₂ -Cl ₂ CC ₆ H ₅	160	75 (1.0)	70 (1.25)	72 (2.0)
C ₆ H ₅ CHCl-ClHCC ₆ H ₅	189	50 (1.5)	45 (3.0)	40 (4.0)

*The elemental analyses values are in good agreement with the calculated values.

With α -chloro- and α -bromotoluenes, only α -iodotoluene is obtained and no coupling reaction is observed. Other systems like CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃, CCl₄ and their bromo and iodo analogues failed to react. Hence we conclude that this coupling reaction is highly specific in nature and occurs only when there is more than one halogen substituent on the same carbon along with a phenyl group, which activates the system.

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A New Route for the Synthesis of Benzofuro-[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-2(H)-one

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THE biological activities of linear furocoumarins known as psoralens are well-known. Psoralen, 8-methoxypsoralen and the trimethyl analogue, trioxsalen are effective photochemotherapeutic agents in the treatment of psoriasis¹. However, they react with DNA by bifunctional mode and are shown to be mutagenic when used in combination with UV-A irradiation². They were also found to be carcinogenic in mice³. Thus monofunctionalised psoralen derivatives are considered safer and it was therefore thought of interest to synthesise benzofuro-[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-2(H)-one and its methyl derivative, a monofunctionalised psoralen by a new route using the technique of tosyloxylation and detosyloxylation. Previously the same compound was synthesised from 7-hydroxycoumarin⁴.

2,4-Dihydroxy acetophenone (1a), on condensation with 2-bromocyclohexanone in presence of potassium carbonate gave 4-(cyclohexan-2-onyloxy)-2-hydroxyacetophenone (2a) which on cyclisation with 0.1 N alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution gave 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-hydroxy-3-acetyldibenzofuran (3a) (Scheme 1). Formation of 3a can be explained on the basis of intramolecular aldol condensation⁴. The phenoxide ion (2a) attacks the exocyclic carbonyl group through the carbanion generated at *para*-position to the phenoxide ion to give 2b followed by abstraction of the proton at the ring junction to regenerate phenoxide ion (2c),

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Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) K₂CO₃, acetone, (ii) 0.1 N alc. KOH, (iii) pulverised Na, Et₂CO, (iv) *p*-tosyl chloride, K₂CO₃, acetone, (v) Zn/HCl, (vi) a: DDQ, C₆H₆, ot; b: Pd/C, Ph₂O.

which on protonation eliminates water from β-hydroxydihydrofuran to give 3a (Scheme 2). Alternate attack at carbonyl group by the carbanion

Scheme 2

generated at *ortho*-position to the phenoxide ion is ruled out, because the pmr spectrum shows two singlets at δ 6.9 and 7.7 corresponding to one proton each attributable to C-1 and C-4 protons respectively.

The compound 3a on condensation with diethylcarbonate⁵ in presence of sodium gave 6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-4-hydroxy-benzofuro[3,2-*g*]benzopyran-2(*H*)-one (4a). Compound 4a on treatment with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride gave its tosyl derivative (5a) which on treatment with zinc dust and hydrochloric acid underwent detosyloxylation⁶ to furnish 6,7,8,9-tetrahydrobenzofuro[2,3-*g*]benzopyran-2(*H*)-one (6a).

Compound 6a on dehydrogenation with DDQ in dry benzene gave benzofuro[2,3-*g*][1]-benzopyran-2(*H*)-one (7a).

Similarly, starting from 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (1b) and following the same series of reactions, 11-methylbenzofuro[3,2-*g*][1]benzopyran-2(*H*)-one (7b) was obtained. The structures of all these compounds were confirmed by their pmr spectra.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Pmr spectra are recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard. Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

4-Cyclohexan-2-onyloxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone (2a): A mixture of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (6.0 g), bromocyclohexone (5.2 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (15.0 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (150 ml) for 8 h. It was then worked out as usual. The product obtained was purified by column chromatography using petroleum ether-benzene (1:1) mixture. It was crystallised from benzenepetroleum ether mixture as colourless crystals (4.5 g), m.p. 136° (Found: C, 67.92; H, 6.47. C₁₄H₁₆O₄ requires: C, 67.74; H, 6.45%).

4-Cyclohexan-2-onyloxy-2-hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone (2b): It was prepared according to the procedure described for 2a starting from 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone and crystallised from benzene, (60%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 69.12; H, 6.99. C₁₅H₁₈O₄ requires: C, 68.70; H, 6.87%); δ (CDCl₃) 2.2 (3H, s, C₃CH₃), 2.55 (3H, s, COCH₃), 1.7–2.6 (8H, m, all CH₂), 4.7 (1H, t, –O–CH–CO), 6.2 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₆-H) and 7.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₅-H).

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-hydroxy-3-acetyldibenzofuran (3a): 4-Cyclohexan-2-onyloxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone (1.0 g) was dissolved in 0.1 N alcoholic KOH (100 ml) and refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The excess of alcohol was then distilled off and the content poured onto ice. On acidification with concentrated HCl, the resultant product was purified by column chromatography using benzene. It crystallised from benzene, (0.6 g), m.p. 182° (Found: C, 73.50; H, 6.50. C₁₄H₁₄O₃ requires: C, 73.50; H, 6.09%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.6–2.0 (4H, m, –CH₂– at C-6 and C-7), 2.4–2.8 (4H, m, CH₂ at C-5 and C-8), 2.6 (3H, s, COCH₃), 6.9 (1H, s, C-1), 7.7 (1H, s, C-4) and 12.0 (1H, s, chelated OH).

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-hydroxy-1-methyl-3-acetyldibenzofuran (3b): It was prepared according to the procedure described for 3a starting from 2b. It was crystallised from benzene, (68%), m.p. 148° (Found: C, 73.35; H, 6.62. C₁₅H₁₆O₃ requires: C, 73.77; H, 6.56%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.7–2.0 (4H, m, –CH₂– at C-6 and C-7), 2.45 (3H, s, C₁-CH₃), 2.5–2.8 (4H, m, CH₂ at C-5 and C-8), 2.7 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.5 (1H, s, C₄-H) and 12.6 (1H, s, chelated OH at C-2).

6,7,8,9-Tetrahydro-4-hydroxybenzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (4a): Compound **3a** (1.0 g) dissolved in diethyl carbonate (10.0 ml), was added slowly to pulverised Na (1.0 g) and heated on a water-bath for 10 h. Alcohol was then added to decompose unreacted Na metal and the content poured in ice-cold water and acidified with concentrated HCl. The product was crystallised from alcohol, (0.8 g), m.p. 280° (Found: C, 70.09; H, 4.97. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires: C, 70.33; H, 4.69%); δ (DMSO- d_6 , TMS) 1.6–2.0 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_7 and C_8), 2.4–2.8 (4H, m, C_6 and C_9 - CH_2), 5.4 (1H, s, C_3 -H), 7.25 (1H, s, C_{11} -H) and 7.65 (1H, s, C_5 -H).

11-Methyl-4-hydroxy-6,7,8,9-tetrahydrobenzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (4b): It was prepared according to the procedure described for **4a** starting from **3b**. It crystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 301° (Found: C, 70.93; H, 4.70. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires: C, 71.11; H, 5.19%).

6,7,8,9-Tetrahydro-4-p-tosyloxy-benzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (5a): A mixture of **4a** (1.0 g), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (1.0 g) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4.0 g) was refluxed in dry acetone (100 ml) for 14 h and then worked out as usual. The resulting solid was washed several times with sodium bicarbonate solution. It was purified by column chromatography using benzene as eluent and crystallised from benzene, (0.8 g) m.p. 211° (Found: C, 64.84; H, 4.50. $C_{22}H_{18}O_6S$ requires: C, 64.39; H, 4.39%); δ (DMSO- d_6 , TMS) 1.6–2.0 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_7 and C_8), 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3 of tosyl group), 2.4–2.8 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_6 and C_9), 6.25 (1H, s, C_3 -H), 7.05 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_{21} -H), 7.9 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_3 -H), 7.3 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_{51} -H), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_{61} -H), 7.45 (1H, s, C_5 -H) and 7.75 (1H, s, C_{11} -H).

6,7,8,9-Tetrahydro-11-methyl-4-p-tosyloxybenzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (5b): It was prepared according to the procedure described for **5a** starting from **4b**. It crystallised from benzene, (65%), m.p. 227° (Found: C, 65.49; H, 4.57. $C_{23}H_{20}O_6S$ requires: C, 65.09; H, 4.72); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.65–2.1 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_7 and C_8), 2.55 (6H, ss, C_{11} - CH_3 and CH_3 of tosyl group), 2.4–2.8 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_6 and C_9), 6.15 (1H, s, C_3 -H), 7.4 (2H, s, C_{21} and C_3 -H), 7.8 (1H, s, C_{51} -H), 7.9 (1H, s, C_{61} -H) and 7.36 (1H, s, C_5 -H).

6,7,8,9-Tetrahydrobenzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (6a): Compound **5a** (1.0 g) was dissolved in benzene-alcohol (1:10) mixture (400 ml). To it zinc dust (3.0 g) and concentrated HCl (10 ml) were added and refluxed on a sand-bath for 1 h. The excess benzene-alcohol mixture was distilled off and the content was filtered hot and poured over ice (30 g). The oil obtained was extracted with ether and purified by preparative tlc using benzene to give a solid product which crystallised from benzene, (0.2 g), m.p. 150° (Found: C, 75.40; H, 5.15. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$ requires: C, 75.00; H, 5.00%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.7–2.1 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_7 and C_8), 2.4–2.8 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_6 and C_9), 6.25 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_3 -H),

7.75 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_4 -H), 7.25 (1H, s, C_{11} -H) and 7.32 (1H, s, C_5 -H).

6,7,8,9-Tetrahydro-11-methyl-benzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (6b): It was prepared according to the procedure described for **6a** starting from **5b**. It was crystallised from benzene, (55%), m.p. 168° (Found: C, 75.10; H, 5.77. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires: C, 75.59; H, 5.51%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.6–2.0 (4H, m, CH_2 at C_7 and C_8), 2.4–2.85 (4H, m, C_6 - CH_2 and C_{11} - CH_2), 2.55 (3H, s, C_{11} - CH_3), 6.3 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_3 -H), 7.8 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_4 -H) and 7.25 (1H, s, C_5 -H).

Benzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (7a): To compound **6a** (0.2 g) dissolved in dry benzene, DDQ (0.4 g) dissolved in dry benzene was added and refluxed for 6 h. It was then filtered, the excess benzene distilled off and the remaining benzene was passed through silica gel. The product was crystallised from benzene, (0.1 g) m.p. 207° (lit.⁷ 202–03°) (Found: C, 76.05; H, 3.44. $C_{15}H_8O_3$ requires: C, 76.08; H; 3.39%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 6.35 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_3 -H), doublet for C_4 proton mixed with multiplet and 7.2–8.0 (7H, m, all remaining ArH).

11-Methyl-benzofuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-2(H)-one (7b): A mixture of **6b** (0.3 g) and Pd/C (10%; 0.25 g) was refluxed in diphenyl ether (5.0 ml) for 12 h. It was then filtered hot and poured into petroleum ether and the resulting solid was crystallised from benzene, (0.18 g), m.p. 226° (Found: C, 75.95; H, 4.37. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires: C, 76.00; H, 4.00%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.6 (3H, s, C_{11} - CH_3), 6.3 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C_3 -H) and 7.1–7.9 (6H, m, all remaining ArH).

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